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Undergraduate Students' Concerns about the Use of Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA) in a Nigerian University

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Abstract

Assessment of large classes is a critical issue that can be addressed through the advances of Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA). This study involved three hundred and fifty nine (359) undergraduate students (176 males and 183 females) drawn through disproportionate stratified random sampling technique from six faculties (Education, Arts, Medical and Allied Medical Sciences, Sciences, Social Sciences and Management Sciences) in University of Calabar, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to identify envisaged problems in the use of Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA) for both assessment for learning (AFL) and Assessment of Learning (AOL) from the study perspective. The researchers also tried to find out if the students' concerns about the use of Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA) were related to the courses they offer, the year of study, their sex as well as their parental educational level using a valid and reliable 25-item Computer Assisted Assessment Questionnaire (CAAQ) designed by the researchers. Data analysis was done using percentages. Discussions and recommendation were made.

Key words: Assessment, Assessment for learning, Assessment of learning, Large class size.

INTRODUCTION

Computer Aided Assessment (CAA) is a subset of the learning technology. Learning technology is basically the application of technology for the enhancement of teaching, learning and assessment. The importance of CAA becomes crucial with rising student number on campuses, the stretch on teachers' time and psyche and incidences of man-made or natural disasters that may affect file-storage.

Among the many advantages of new technologies is the fact that it enables students to receive immediate feedback and for teachers to carry out rapid and continuous assessment.

Strategies used by academic staff to overcome challenges posed by assessment of large classes include group assessment and online assessment among others. These methods have their merits and short-comings. The disadvantages of online assessment, as given by this author Wasyanju (2005) are as follows:

- i) It adds nothing to students' learning or in some cases, it hinders students' learning.
- ii) It concentrates on true/false answers and it therefore, encourages lower level cognition skills.
- iii) It encourages narrow reproduction of answers rather than critical evaluation.

Sheader, Gouldsborough and Grady (2006) are of the opinion that although it is acknowledged that "multiple choice questions" (MCQ) are easy to mark, it is not always appropriate or desirable to offer assessment in this form.

Statement of problem

This study seeks to find out from the students' perspective, their acceptance or non-acceptance of CAA as well as the concerns they envisage in the use of CAA for both Assessment of Learning (AOL) and Assessment for Learning (AFL).

Purpose of study

The study was designed to answer a main question; 'how feasible is CAA in the University of Calabar, Nigeria considering the advantages? Specifically the investigators were interested in finding out if undergraduate students sampled were favourably disposed to a shift in assessment from the traditional paper-and-pencil type to the use of CAA. More specifically, we were interested in finding out if the response pattern of students would depend on:

- i) The course of study
- ii) Their year of study
- iii) The sex of the student
- iv) Parental educational level of the students.

Research questions

Four (4) research questions formed the focus of this study.

Research question 1:

What is the disposition (favourable or unfavourable) of undergraduate students in different courses of study of University of Calabar as regards the use of CAA for (i) assignment (ii) test (iii) examination?

Research question 2:

How do final year students perceive the use of CAA for (i) assignment (ii) test (iii) examination as compared to other undergraduate students?

Research question 3:

How do male undergraduate students perceive the use of CAA for (i) assignment (ii) test (iii) examination as compared to their female counterparts?

Research question 4:

How will the perception of the use of CAA for (i) assignment (ii) test (iii) examination differ among undergraduate students with different parental educational background.

METHODOLOGY

Design

This is a survey of the ex-post-facto nature. This design was adopted because the investigation did not manipulate the variables but just studied the outcome of the variables as observed among the sample studied (Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim & Ekuri, 2004).

Sampling technique and sample

Disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to select the subjects for this study. The stratification was based on course of study, year of study, sex of students and their parental educational level.

The sample so selected consisted of 359 undergraduate students (176 males; 183 females) enrolled in 6 courses (Education, Arts, Medical and Allied Medical Sciences, Sciences, Social Sciences and Management Sciences). Out of the number sampled, 105 were in their final year while 254 were non-final year students. In terms of parental educational level, 163 came from homes where at least one parent had a minimum of a bachelor's degree while 196 had parents with qualifications less than a first degree.

Instrumentation

A questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of two major parts. The first part sought information about the students' demographic variables (course of study, year of study, sex and parental educational level), while the second part of the questionnaire focused on undergraduate students' acceptability of CAA for assignments, tests and examination and their concerns about the use of CAA for these areas. The "use of CAA" scale consisted of 25 items.

To ensure construct validity of the scale, items were generated from prior exploratory interviews across groups of undergraduate students during various interactions in formal and informal settings. Only concerns shared by over 50% of such students were included as questionnaire items.

Data collection procedure

Three hundred and sixty (360) copies of the questionnaires were administered to the selected sample through contact persons in the six different courses over a period of one week. Out of this number three hundred and fifty nine (359) copies were retrieved giving a return rate of about (99.7%).

Data analysis

On the issue of whether the undergraduate students were favourably or unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA, the researchers considered the uses for purposes of (i) assignments (ii) tests (iii) examination. They were to indicate by ticking 'yes' or 'no' to questions that focused on these 3 areas. Selecting 'yes' indicated they were in support of the use and 'no' indicated they were not in support of the use of CAA for the areas under scrutiny. Percentages were computed for the four (4) research questions to provide the required answers.

Furthermore, since the investigators were also interested in finding out areas of concern of students as it related to the use of CAA; five (5) key areas were delineated from earlier exploratory interviews with some students. Their concerns were identified as lack of computer/internet skills, teachers' supervisory control over the conduct of examination, security/leakage of questions, ratio of students to available computers and poor/interruption of electricity supply.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the data analysis are presented in appropriate tables in the sequence of the research questions.

Research question 1

How do students undertaking different courses of study perceive CAA when used for (i) assignments (ii) tests (iii) examination as compared to other undergraduate students?

Analysis was done using percentages to find out if the undergraduate students sampled were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for formative and summative assessment purposes. Results of the analyses are shown in Table 1a, 1b and 1c respectively.

Undergraduate students' disposition favourable (F) and unfavourable (U) towards the use of CAA for assignments, tests and examination by course of study.

Table 1a

s/n	Course of study	Disposition about CAA for assignments				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Education	38	18.7	17	10.9	55
2.	Arts	35	17.2	24	15.4	59
3.	Medical and Allied Sciences	34	16.8	39	25.0	73
4.	Sciences	28	13.8	33	21.2	61
5.	Social sciences	32	15.8	16	10.3	48
6.	Management sciences	36	17.7	27	17.3	63
	Total	203	100	156	100	359

Table 1b

s/n	Course of study	Disposition about CAA for tests				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Education	39	17.6	16	11.7	55
2.	Arts	38	17.1	21	15.3	59
3.	Medical and Allied Sciences	39	17.6	34	24.8	73
4.	Sciences	35	15.8	26	19.0	61
5.	Social sciences	30	13.5	18	13.1	48
6.	Management sciences	41	18.5	22	16.1	63
	Total	222	100	137	100	359

Table 1c

s/n	Course of study	Disposition about CAA for examination				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Education	40	18.3	15	10.6	55
2.	Arts	37	17.0	22	15.6	59
3.	Medical and Allied Sciences	36	16.5	37	26.2	73
4.	Sciences	33	15.1	28	19.9	61
5.	Social sciences	31	14.2	17	12.1	48
6.	Management sciences	41	18.8	22	15.6	63
	Total	218	100%	141	100	359

The information in Table 1a, 1b and 1c respectively shows the responses to undergraduate disposition favourable (F) and unfavourable (u) towards the use of CAA for assignments, tests and examination. Table 1a shows that only 156 or (43.5%) undergraduate students of the total sampled students were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for learning while 203 or (56.5%) undergraduate students were unfavorably disposed.

In Table 1b, the information revealed that only 137 or (38.2%) of the sample undergraduate students were favourably disposed to CAA for tests while 222 or (61.8%) students were not favourably disposed to the use of CAA for learning.

On the same note, the information in table1c shows that only 141 or (39.3%) undergraduate students were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for examination while 218 (60.7%) students of the sampled undergraduate students were unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA for examination. Generally, it is seen that undergraduate students seem to prefer the conventional assessment approach to CAA in assignments, tests and examination.

Research question 2

How do final year students perceive the use of CAA for (i) assignments (ii) tests (iii) examination as compared to other undergraduate student. Analysis was done using percentages to find out how undergraduate final year students perceive the use of CAA for formative and summative assessment purposes. The results of the analysis for the three approaches are presented in table 2a, 2b and 2c respectively.

Table 2a, 2b and 2c: Use of CAA for assignments, tests and examination by year of study.

Table 2a

S/n	Year of study	Disposition about CAA for assignment				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Final year	61	58	44	42	105
2.	Others	142	55.9	112	44.1	254
	Total	203		156		359

Table 2b

S/n	Year of study	Disposition about CAA for test				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Final year	62	60	43	40	105
2.	Others	160	63	94	37	254
	Total	222		137		359

Table 2c

S/n	Year of study	Disposition about CAA for examination				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Final year	63	60	42	40	105
2.	Others	154	61	99	39	254
	Total	218		141		359

The information in Table 2a, 2b and 2c respectively shows the final year undergraduate students' perception of the use of CAA for assignments, tests, and examination. The result revealed that in Table 2a, using CAA as a means of assessment for assignment, 61(58%) of the final year students, were unfavourable, while 44 (42%) respondents were favourable to the use of CAA. For all other students, 142 (55.9%) were unfavourably disposed, while 112 (44.1%) were favourable to the use of CAA for assignments.

The result in Table 2b shows the use of CAA for test as perceived by final year undergraduate students. From the table, 62 or (60%) students were unfavourably disposed while 43 (40%) students were favourably disposed to CAA. All other sampled undergraduate students 60(63%), were unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA for test while only 94(37%) were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for test.

In table 2c, 63 (60%) of the final year students were unfavourable to CAA use (for examination) as assessment of learning. All other sampled students numbering 154 (61%) of the students were not favourably disposed to CAA use for examination. Only 99 (39%) of students were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for examination.

Research question 3

How do male undergraduate students perceive the use of CAA for (i) assignments (ii) tests (iii) examination as compared to their female counterparts.

Analysis was done using percentages to find out if the sampled undergraduate students were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for both formative and summative assessment purposes. The results of the analysis is presented in Table 3a, 3b, and 3c respectively.

Table 3a, 3b and 3c: Use of CAA for assignments, tests and examination by sex

Table 3a

S/n	Sex	Disposition about CAA for assignments				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Male	102	58	74	42	176
2.	Female	101	55	82	45	183
	Total	203	57	156	43	359

Table 3b

S/n	Sex	Disposition about CAA for tests				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Male	97	55	79	45	176
2.	Female	125	68	58	32	183
	Total	222	61.8	137	38.2	359

Table 3c

S/n	Sex	Disposition about CAA for examination				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	Male	105	59.7	71	40.3	176
2.	Female	113	61.7	70	38.3	183
	Total	218	60.7	141	39.3	359

The information in Table 3a, 3b and 3c respectively reveals that for assignments, male and female responses were almost the same. 102 (58%) male respondents of the total sample male undergraduate students were unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA for assignment. On the other hand 74 (42%) male respondents were favourably disposed to the use of CAA for assignment as an approach to assessment for learning. Also, 101 (55%) of female respondents were unfavourably disposed, while 82(45%) were favourable. This result shows that both male and female students were not favourably disposed to CAA for assessment for learning.

The response in section 3b shows students' opinion about CAA for test as a means of assessment for learning. Out of a total of 183 female undergraduate students 125 or (68%) are unfavourable. While only 58 (32%) respondents of sampled female students said 'yes' to CAA for test. For their male counterparts, out of the total of 176, 97 or (55%) did not welcome CAA for test. The remaining proportion, 79 or (45%) male were in favour of CAA for test.

The general response of both male and female undergraduate students reveals that they were not favourably disposed to the use of CAA for assessment for learning.

The information on section 3c of the table reveals that, of the 176 male students sampled, 105 males or (59.7%) and 113 or (61.7%) females out of the 183 respondents were unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA. On the other hand 71 or (40.3%) male students and 70 or (38.3%) female students were favourably disposed to CAA use for examination. This implies that both male and female undergraduate students were unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA in assessment of learning. The students preferred using the traditional assessment method of paper and pencil for examination.

Research question 4

How will the perception of the use of CAA for (i) assignments (ii) tests (iii) examination differ among undergraduate students with different parental educational background?

The response to the above research question is presented in table 4a, 4b and 4c respectively. The analysis involved the use of percentages to find out the undergraduate students' disposition (favourable or unfavourable) to the use of CAA for assignments, tests and examination, based on students' parental educational background.

Table 4a, 4b and 4c: Use of CAA for assignments, tests and examination by parental educational level.

Table 4a

S/n	Parent educational level	Disposition about CAA for assignment				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	SSCE/Undergraduate	121	61.7	75	38.3	196
2.	B.Sc., M.Sc. and Ph.D	82	50.3	81	49.7	163
	Total	203	56.5	156	43.5	359

Table 4b

S/n	Parental educational level	Disposition about CAA for test				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	SSCE/Undergraduate	128	65.3	68	34.7	196
2.	B.Sc., M.Sc. and Ph.D	94	57.7	69	42.3	163
	Total	222	61.8	137	38.2	359

Table 4c

S/n	Parent educational level	Disposition about CAA for examination				
		U	%	F	%	Total
1.	SSCE/Undergraduate	126	64.3	70	35.7	196
2.	B.Sc., M.Sc. and Ph.D	92	56.4	71	43.6	163
	Total	218	60.7	141	39.3	359

The information in Table 4a shows that for assignment, 121 or (61.7%) undergraduate students from 196 parents with less than first degree representing (54.6%) of total number of parents rejected the use of CAA, while 75 (38.3%) were favourable. Also, 82 or (50.3%) students of parents with first degree or above responded unfavourably, and 81 or (49.7%) were favourable to use of CAA.

Table 4b reveals that for tests, students from parents having less than first degree educational qualification and numbering 128 (or 65.3%), and their counterpart from parents with first degree or above numbering 94 or (57.7%) were unfavourably disposed to the use of CAA. Only 68 or (34.7%) of students from parents having less than first degree and 69 or (42.3%) with parents having higher qualifications accepted the use of CAA.

On examination, the results in Table 3 shows that 126 or (64.3%) from parents with first degree rejected CAA, while a smaller number, 70 or (5.7%) of students of the same socio group said 'yes'.

However, 92 or (56.4%) of students from parents with less than first degree rejected the use of CAA for examination. Also, 71 or (43.6%) of undergraduate students from less educated parents showed preference for CAA for examination. Generally the results indicate that students are not favourably disposed to the use of CAA both for assessment for learning and assessment of learning. A closer look at the table will reveal that the results in table 4a, b and c show that students from highly educated parents than those from parents with low educational background show unfavourable disposition to the use of CAA for both formative and summative assessment. The result finds explanation in Uwakwe (2005), that tests can be biased in favour of the dominant socio group. However, students from affluent homes are expected to be more exposed to the benefits of computer, internet and ICT in general. Therefore, it is surprising that this same group of students showed the least disposition towards the use of CAA as a means of assessment of learning and assessment for learning.

Students' major concerns

It could be seen from the results that whether for assessment of learning (AOL) or assessment for learning (AFL), the students in this study have their own concerns when it comes to accepting CAA as an alternative to the traditional paper and pencil mode of assessment they are used to. Their concerns do not just centre on lack of willingness to accept change. Baseline data that was used to generate questionnaire items showed the following as areas of concern:

1. Lack of computer/internet skills
2. Teachers' supervisory control
3. Security/leakage of questions
4. Ratio of students to available computers
5. Poor/interruption in electricity supply

Results of investigation about students' concerns are shown in table 5 below:

Table 5: Students' major concerns about the use of CAA

S/n	Concerns	Yes	%	No	%	Total
1.	Lack of computer/internet skills	260	72.4	99	27.6	359
2.	Teachers' supervisory control over the conduct of examination	243	67.7	116	32.3	359
3.	Security/leakage of questions	258	71.9	101	28.1	359
4.	Ratio of students available computers	285	79.4	74	20.6	359
5.	Poor/interruption of electricity supply	301	84	58	16	359

Table 5a: Lack of computer/Internet Skills

i. Year of study/computer/internet skill

S/n	Year of study	Internet skill		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Final year	31	74	105
2.	Others	68	186	253
	Total	99	260	359

ii. Course/Computer and internet skill

S/n	Course of study	Internet skill		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Education	15	40	55
2.	Arts	13	46	59

3	Medical and Allied Sciences	22	51	73
4	Sciences	21	40	61
5	Social sciences	15	33	48
6	Management sciences	13	50	63
	Total	99	260	359

iii. Sex/Computer and Internet skill

S/n	Sex	Internet skill		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Male	47	129	176
2.	Female	52	131	183
	Total	99	260	359

iv. Parental educational level/computer and internet skill
Computer/Internet skill

Parental ed level	No	Yes	Total
SSCE/Undergrad	52	144	196
BSc,Msc,Ph.D	47	116	163
Total	99	260	359

Table 5b: Teachers' supervisory control over the conduct of examination

S/n	Teachers' control	Teachers' control		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Male	63	113	176
2.	Female	53	130	183
	Total	116	243	359

Table 5c: Security/Leakage of questions

S/n	Sex	Leakage		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Male	57.3	68	105
2.	Female	64	189	253
	Total	101	258	359

Table 5d: Sex/Large class

S/n	Sex	Large class		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Male	36	140	176
2.	Female	38	145	183
	Total	74	285	359

Table 5e: Concern about poor electricity supply/interruption

S/n	Course of study	Electricity		
		No	Yes	Total
1.	Education	9	46	55
2.	Arts	6	53	59
3.	Medical and Allied Sciences	18	55	73
4.	Sciences	11	50	61
5.	Social sciences	8	40	48
6.	Management sciences	6	57	63
	Total	58	301	359

i. Lack of computer/internet skills

Of the 359 students, 260 or (72.4%) expressed concern in this area while 99 or (27.6%) did not show much concern about the fate of students who fail in their assessment due to inability to use the computer. Out of the 260 (72.4%) undergraduate students that said 'yes' to the use of CAA, (28.5%) i.e., 74 were final year students who perhaps did not pay much attention to the poor computer/internet skills vis-à-vis CAA as they were almost on their way out of school.

However, it is important to note that more female students (131) than males (129) expressed greater concern over the lack of computer and internet skills in the use of CAA. The greatest concern in terms

of course of study, was raised by the undergraduate students of the medical and Allied Medical Sciences. On the whole, in terms of computer/internet skills, the results show that more than half of the total number of respondents sampled from the six courses i.e., 260 or (72.4%) feared that the use of CAA could cause many students to fail in their various tests, assignments and examination due to inability in the use and lack of access to internet.

This finding is in line with the report by Nigerian computer society in Asim (2007), that access to internet and other IT-related tools of learning are very limited in all higher institutions in Nigeria.

ii. Teachers' supervisory control over the conduct of examination

In the traditional assessment method, teachers ensure that students comply with examination regulations in terms of minimizing or eliminating interruption among examinees. One major concern raised by students had to do with teachers' role during the conduct of examination. As many as 243 or (67.7%) of those sampled were concerned that teachers may not be able to control what students do during tests or examination if CAA is adopted.

iii. Security/leakage of questions

In consideration of tests and examination in relation to CAA use, large percentage of students, 258 (71.9%) feared that if students do not take examination at the same time, the use of CAA could lead to leakage of questions. This concern was again more among the females 189 or (74%) than their male counterparts 68 or (26%) as shown in table 5c.

iv. Ratio of students to available computers

Large percentage of students, 285 or (79.4%) feared that if the examination is during school hours, it may take the whole day for students to write batch by batch due to inadequate computers. Further, table 5d shows that more females 145 or (40%) than males 140 or (35.4%), expressed deeper concern that many students cannot write examination at the same venue if CAA is used and therefore, queried the reliability of the assessment if examination is taken at different venues.

v. Concern for poor electricity supply/interruption

The supply of electricity is vital to the use of CAA. This is an area that most undergraduate students expressed concern. The poor power supply coupled with frequent interruption reflected in the finding of this study where well over half of the sampled students 301 or (84%) feared that electricity interruption may likely affect their performances in tests and examination if CAA is used.

In general, the results have shown much fear on the part of undergraduate students over the use of CAA for both formative and summative assessments. Concerns in most cases have been strongly felt among the female than male students. This concern agrees with earlier findings by Barrett and Lally (1999) which indicated that technology based learning may reproduce gender difference within a learning community. Prior to this, earlier studies by Severiens and TenDam (1995) indicate that when using computers, females have been considered to possess a higher level of computer anxiety than males and experience more negative feeling towards computers (Brounma & Davidson, 1994). Ring's (1991) explanation of the negative confidence of female over the male students was based on the fact that males have spent more time with computers at home, work and/or school and that most females are being 'put off' computers at school.

However, previous preliminary research by Dyer (1990) indicates no statistical difference in marks between males and females on similar information technology courses in years when assessment did not include objective testing or their delivery by computer. The concern, the author emphasized, is to ensure that female undergraduate students are not disadvantaged by the introduction of CAA, which may result in lower marks by them in the same assessment, text or examination taken by males.

Conclusion

Based on the results of these findings, it could be concluded that the undergraduate students of University of Calabar, are not favourable to the use of CAA for either Assessment for Learning (AFL) or Assessment of Learning (AOL). They are genuinely concerned about the following: lack of computer/internet skills, teachers' supervisory control over the conduct of examination, security/leakage of questions, ratio of students to available computer and poor/interruption in electricity supply.

Recommendation

The undergraduate students should be enlightened as to the importance of the use of CAA.

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